

Intelligent automation is about creating synergies between robotic process automation (RPA), cognitive, chatbots and artificial intelligence (AI)

As digital technologies and concepts evolve at a very rapid pace, we are hearing company leaders raise the following questions:

- What are the next steps after Robotic Process Automation (RPA)?
- How Artificial Intelligence (AI), chatbots and RPA are linked together, which one brings value to the other?
- We have already implemented some chatbots, do we really need to implement RPA?
- Our competitors are already using AI. Should we be doing the same? Are we late?
- Where should we start our intelligent automation journey? How can we get prepared for the next steps in this journey, and make sure we build this journey in a sustainable and consistent manner?

Companies are going through the intelligent automation journey (or digital operations journey) by digitalizing their process activities using robots. Their goals are mainly to improve business efficiency, reduce costs, enhance customer experience (internal and external clients), and reach a higher level of process excellence (e.g., improve quality, accuracy).

The "intelligent automation journey" framework describes four main generations of robots that companies are implementing, their characteristics and associated benefits.

It is more logical to deploy the robot generations in a sequential order, starting from generation one to four (e.g., implementing traditional RPA before implementing the next ones). In doing so, companies will be able to avoid experiencing the "empty shell effect."

Above all, to create a maximum of value out of this journey, effective interactions between the generations of robots need to be implemented. New generations are not meant to replace existing ones, but instead, they are to work hand-in-hand. We have identified that these interactions create synergies, where each generation will add value beyond its single intended benefit.

Ref to my complete article for more detail:

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<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/from-robotic-process-automation-rpa-artificial-ai-journey-bornet>

Note: the views reflected above are the views of the author and do not necessarily reflect the views of the global EY organization or its member firms

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Pascal has over 18 years' experience leading large business transformation programs for multinational companies, with a particular focus on Digital Workforce, Robotic Process Automation (RPA), Artificial Intelligence (AI), Global Business Services (GBS) and Shared Services Centers (SSC). For the last 14 years at EY, he has managed more than 100 projects, across industries and functions, involving multi-million dollar budgets, and significant complexity including changes in process, organization and technology.

Since 2014, Pascal has been leading Intelligent Automation for EY Asia Pacific. Intelligent Automation, which includes RPA, cognitive, machine learning, intelligent chatbots, analytics and artificial intelligence, is a strategic area of growth for EY. Pascal has successfully driven the set-up of the governance, and managed the strategic direction of this new practice, including building the teams and creating the EY Asia Pacific Robotics Center of Excellence.

He has successfully supported 50+ clients designing and deploying their Intelligent Automation projects with a focus on improving business efficiency, reducing costs (typically 10 to 30%), enhancing customer experience, and reaching a higher level of process excellence (improve quality, accuracy and compliance). He has ensured the success of these projects by adopting a transformational approach, incorporating governance design, operating model changes, change management, senior executives support & stakeholders alignment, digital workforce & shared service centers considerations, and process optimization.

Pascal strongly believes in the powerful combination of robots and people. He is passionate about new technologies, and about creating a better world for the new generations.

Pascal is a licensed CPA from USA (AICPA), he holds a Master of Finance from ESC Saint Etienne - EM Lyon (France), a Master of Business from NUS (National University of Singapore), and his MBA from UCLA Anderson (University of California, Los Angeles).